

1 This paper is a preprint, version 3, 2024/08/31. This paper has not been peer-reviewed.

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3 **Minority stress and psychological distress among sexual and gender expansive people:**
4 **Evidence from Kazakhstan**

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STATEMENTS AND DECLARATIONS

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Acknowledgements

We thank the participants for their courage and time in sharing their stories. We thank the project staff of the Columbia University Global Health Research Center of Central Asia for their commitment and care given to the execution of study activities.

Conflict of Interest

The authors have no conflicts of interest to declare.

Funding

This study was supported by grant R01DA040513 (PI: Wu) from the National Institute on Drug Abuse. Caitlin Laughney's time was supported by grants T32MH019139 (PI: Sandfort) and P30MH043620 (PI: Ramien) from the National Institute of Mental Health. Emily Allen Paine's time was supported by grants K01MH128117 (PI: Paine) and P30MH43520 (PI: Remien) from the National Institute of Mental Health.

Data Availability

Deidentified data used in this study could be made available from the corresponding author upon reasonable request.

43 **Abstract**

44 There is a critical gap in minority stress research in Kazakhstan, where the rights and
45 dignity of sexual and gender expansive (SGE) people have been under increasing threat. This
46 brief report investigated minority stress processes in a sample of cisgender gay, bisexual, and
47 other men (MSM) and transgender and nonbinary individuals who have sex with men (TSM)
48 enrolled in a behavioral HIV prevention trial in Kazakhstan. Baseline data from 629 MSM and
49 TSM were used to analyze the rates of and associations between victimization, discrimination,
50 and internalized stigma and symptoms of depression, anxiety, and stress. Descriptive analyses
51 showed that 68% of the study participants experienced at least one of 16 forms of victimization
52 and 32% one of 8 domains of discrimination within the past six months. Meanwhile, 28%, 37%,
53 and 21% of the study participants reported experiencing at least moderate levels of depression,
54 anxiety, and stress, respectively, within the past one week. Multivariable regression analyses
55 identified victimization and discrimination as significant predictors of all psychological distress
56 indicators. Internalized stigma significantly predicted depression. The study findings
57 corroborated the minority stress model for MSM and TSM in Kazakhstan.

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59 **Key words**

60 Minority stress, psychological distress, men who have sex with men, transgender health,
61 Kazakhstan

INTRODUCTION

Widespread stigma associated with sexual orientation and gender identity and expression (SOGIE) has been routinely reported to be enacted through victimization and discrimination across multiple domains, including healthcare and familial systems (ECOM, 2022; Knight, 2015; Kospakov et al., 2023). Recently, the government of Kazakhstan began reviewing a petition for banning any public display or discussion of LGBTQ identities, as such are regarded as propaganda causing harm to children (OHCHR, 2024). This development is continuation of prior attempts in Kazakhstan (Amnesty International, 2015) and is similar to developments in Russia, whose ban on “LGBTQ propaganda” has been gaining traction across Central Asia and post-soviet states (HRW, 2015, 2023; Light, 2024; Masci, 2014). These incidents not only render the environment hostile for sexual and gender expansive (SGE) people, but may also exacerbate their health risks. Among gay, bisexual, and other men (MSM) and transgender and nonbinary individuals who have sex with men (TSM), SOGIE stigma-based victimization and discrimination have been associated with higher rates of earlier sexual debut and interruption to HIV testing and treatment (Laughney et al., 2023; Paine et al., 2023).

Robust evidence illustrates poor mental health outcomes among SGE people globally (Pinna et al., 2022; Plöderl & Tremblay, 2015). The predominant model for explaining mental health challenges and disparities in these populations is the minority stress model, which postulates that SOGIE stigma induces adverse events and conditions, conceptualized as minority stressors (Meyer, 2003; Testa et al., 2015). These stressors place excess stress burden on SGE people, thus instigating such maladaptive responses as psychological distress among this population (Meyer, 2003; Testa et al., 2015). Nascent but growing research on minority stress in Central Asia and post-Soviet states has demonstrated that victimization, discrimination, and

85 internalized stigma are linked to depression, anxiety, and stress among SGE people (Ibragimov
86 & Wong, 2018; Kranz et al., 2023). A study in Russia found that legalization of the ban on
87 LGBTQ propaganda intensified minority stress among MSM (Hylton et al., 2017).

88 Notwithstanding the risk of psychological distress, research on mental health of SGE
89 people in Kazakhstan is extremely scarce. One study explored the potential role of SOGIE
90 stigma-based shame in suicidality among queer people in Kazakhstan (Levitanus, 2022). To
91 bridge this critical gap, the present study investigated the rates of and associations between
92 minority stressors and psychological distress in a sample of MSM and TSM in Kazakhstan.

93 **METHODS**

94 **Participants and Procedures**

95 Data for the present study came from a U.S. NIDA-funded behavioral HIV prevention
96 trial in Kazakhstan (NCT02786615). Briefly, the parent study sought to test the efficacy of a
97 novel crowdsourcing intervention in increasing the number of MSM and TSM who illicitly use
98 drugs in the HIV care continuum in Kazakhstan (Wu et al., 2024). The inclusion criteria for the
99 clinical trial were: being at least 18 years old; being assigned male at birth or having ever
100 identified as male; having consensual sex with a man within the past 12 months; and illicitly
101 using alcohol, drugs, or both in the past three months.

102 MSM and TSM were recruited from online and physical LGBTQ-branded venues. Those
103 meeting inclusion criteria were invited to complete the baseline survey in a private research
104 office. Participants completing the survey verbally provided informed consent and received a gift
105 card or phone credit valued at 5,000 Kazakhstani Tenge (~10 USD) as compensation. The
106 Institutional Review Boards of Columbia University and Al-Farabi Kazakh National University
107 reviewed and approved the study procedures.

108 The present study considered baseline data collected during the trial (July 2018-March
109 2022) that yielded a sample size of 629 participants (age in years: range=18-68; median=27). In
110 this sample, 560 (89.0%) identified as cis men, 36 (6.0%) as trans women, 29 (4.6%) as
111 nonbinary, and 2 (<1.0%) as trans men. With respect to sexual orientation, the majority identified
112 as gay (51.4%), followed by bisexual or pansexual (46.9%), and straight (1.7%).

113 **Measures**

114 **Psychological Distress**

115 Psychological distress was assessed using the DASS-21, a short form of Lovibond and
116 Lovibond's Depression Anxiety Stress Scales (DASS) (Lovibond & Lovibond, 1995). The
117 DASS-21 consists of three seven-item subscales measuring psycho-somatic symptoms of
118 depression, anxiety, and stress. Participants reported past one-week occurrences of each
119 symptom on a four-point scale ranging from "did not apply to me at all" (0) to "applied to me
120 very much, or most of the time" (3). Responses were summed and doubled to obtain the scores
121 for depression ($\alpha=.855$), anxiety ($\alpha=.768$), and stress ($\alpha=.825$), with higher scores representing
122 greater distress. Prior research has indicated that scores of ≥ 14 , ≥ 10 , and ≥ 19 correspond with
123 experiencing moderate to extremely severe levels of depression, anxiety, and stress, respectively
124 (Lovibond & Lovibond, 1995).

125 **Minority Stressors**

126 Victimization and discrimination were assessed using Herek and Berrill's measure of
127 anti-gay violence (Herek & Berrill, 1990). In the victimization subscale, we added two questions
128 regarding being outed and being threatened to be outed and two questions regarding insults and
129 threats of physical violence on social media. Participants reported past six-month experiences of
130 16 different forms of victimization and 8 domains of discrimination (e.g., workplace, healthcare,

131 family) by responding “never” (0), “once” (1), or “twice or more” (2); responses exceeding
132 “never” were collapsed to denote any experience of victimization or discrimination. These
133 responses were summed to generate count variables for victimization ($\alpha=.861$) and
134 discrimination ($\alpha=.648$).

135 Internalized stigma was assessed using the nine-item Internalized Homophobia Scale
136 (IHS) (Herek et al., 1998). On a five-point scale ranging from “strongly disagree” (0) to
137 “strongly agree” (4), participants reported how much they agreed with statements about negative
138 beliefs regarding being MSM or TSM. Responses were summed to obtain the overall IHS score
139 ($\alpha=.885$), with higher scores corresponding with greater stigma.

140 **Sociodemographic Characteristics**

141 Participants self-reported residence, citizenship, legal marital status, age, education level,
142 employment status, housing arrangement, living arrangement, gender modality, sexual
143 orientation, and HIV status.

144 **Data Analysis**

145 All statistical analyses were performed on SPSS version 29 (IBM Corp., 2023), with
146 significance set at $p<.05$. Accounting for potential clustering of data by residence, generalized
147 linear mixed models were used to assess the associations between minority stressors and
148 psychological distress indicators. All models were adjusted for sociodemographic characteristics.

149 **RESULTS**

150 The mean scores for the DASS-21 subscales were: 9.0 ($SD=7.6$) for depression; 8.0
151 ($SD=6.9$) for anxiety; and 13.0 ($SD=8.1$) for stress. The distributions of the DASS-21 subscale
152 scores illustrated that 174 (27.7%), 235 (37.4%), and 133 (21.1%) participants experienced at
153 least moderate levels of depression, anxiety, and stress, respectively. In this sample, 430 (68.4%)

154 and 200 (31.8%) participants reported experiencing at least single instances of victimization and
 155 discrimination, respectively, within the past six months.

156 The results of the regression analyses are summarized in Table 1. Victimization was
 157 significantly associated with symptoms of depression ($B=0.32$, $SE=0.06$, $p<.01$), anxiety
 158 ($B=0.42$, $SE=0.07$, $p<.01$), and stress ($B=0.51$, $SE=0.21$, $p=.02$). Discrimination was also
 159 significantly associated with symptoms of depression ($B=0.71$, $SE=0.22$, $p<.01$), anxiety
 160 ($B=0.65$, $SE=0.2321$, $p=.04$), and stress ($B=0.87$, $SE=0.21$, $p<.01$). Internalized stigma was
 161 significantly associated with symptoms of depression ($B=0.15$, $SE=0.03$, $p<.01$).

Table 1. Associations between minority stressors and psychological distress symptoms
 ($N=629$)

	Depression score <i>B (SE)</i>	Anxiety score <i>B (SE)</i>	Stress score <i>B (SE)</i>
# Victimization forms	0.32 (0.06)**	0.42 (0.07)**	0.51 (0.21)*
# Discrimination domains	0.71 (0.22)**	0.65 (0.32)*	0.87 (0.21)**
Internalized stigma score	0.15 (0.03)**	0.02 (0.04)	0.08 (0.05)

* $p<.05$, ** $p<.01$

All models were adjusted for citizenship, legal marital status, age, education level, employment status, housing arrangement, living arrangement, gender modality, sexual orientation, and HIV status.

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DISCUSSION

164 In this study involving MSM and TSM in Kazakhstan, victimization and discrimination
 165 were significantly associated with all psychological distress indicators. Internalized stigma
 166 significantly predicted symptoms of depression, albeit to a lesser extent compared with
 167 victimization and discrimination; it was not significantly associated with anxiety or stress. A
 168 recent study involving LGBT adults in Russia similarly found weaker effects of internalized
 169 stigma, compared with discrimination, on depression and anxiety (Kranz et al., 2023). According
 170 to Meyer, victimization and discrimination are objective events (i.e., occurring independently of
 171 one's personal identification with a stigmatized identity), whereas internalized stigma is more
 172 subjective (i.e., contingent upon one's personal identification with a stigmatized identity)

173 (Meyer, 2003). As the IHS was developed for measuring internalized homophobia, participants
174 who did not identify as gay might have found these experiences less relevant, thus weakening the
175 effects.

176 We have noted several limitations in the present study. First, as alluded above, the IHS
177 most likely centered the experiences of gay men. Future research should assess internalized
178 stigma associated with members of the diverse SOGIE community to adequately capture and
179 address their influence on psychological distress among MSM and TSM in Kazakhstan. Next,
180 the study used a cross-sectional design, thus limiting temporal inferences in the minority stress
181 processes. However, the differences in the recall periods (i.e., past six months for victimization
182 and discrimination and past one week for depression, anxiety, and stress symptoms) could allow
183 for some inference of temporality. Finally, the use of non-probability sampling methods and the
184 aforementioned inclusion criteria might have influenced the sample, thus limiting finding
185 generalizability. The study sample included participants contending with multiple health risks,
186 such as HIV and illicit drug use, both of which are known to be associated with violence and
187 psychological distress (Lee et al., 2022). Therefore, it is possible that the participants were more
188 vulnerable to minority stress.

189 SOGIE-related stigma-based minority stress is on the rise in Kazakhstan, warranting
190 investigation and elimination of its adverse mental health impact. This brief report extends the
191 state-of-the-art literature on minority stress beyond Western countries and cultures by providing
192 the first empirical evidence for minority stress processes among SGE people in Kazakhstan. The
193 study's findings support the minority stress model, especially addressing victimization and
194 discrimination, when promoting mental health among MSM and TSM in Kazakhstan.

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